

PGP ACTIVITIES OF ANTARCTIC ACTINOMYCETES FROM GALINDEZ ISLAND AND GENOMIC ANALYSIS OF *STREPTOMYCES* SP. DA 82-17

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Global climate change is causing a decline in yields, while excessive fertilizer use degrades soil fertility. Meanwhile, plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB) enhance crop growth. Identifying PGPBs with plant growth-stimulating potential is a global trend in agricultural inoculation. The extreme Antarctic conditions—low temperatures, high UV radiation, and nutrient limitations—have driven microbial adaptations. These bacteria can synthesize specialized metabolites with PGP activity.

The aim of this study was to identify PGP strains among 100 actinomycete strains isolated from the rhizosphere of *Deschampsia antarctica* (Galindez Island, Antarctica). The strains were obtained from the Microbial Culture Collection of Antibiotic Producers at Ivan Franko National University of Lviv. Among the isolates, siderophore producers with affinity to metal ions of Fe³⁺ (15%), Cu²⁺ (55%), Ni²⁺ (47%), Zn²⁺ (47%), or Mn²⁺ (51%) were identified. Additionally, 21% solubilized insoluble compounds of P, while 34% solubilized Zn, following Tirry et al. (2018). Solubilizing insoluble compounds of P and Zn with siderophore production plays a crucial role in PGP by enhancing nutrient bioavailability, uptake, and stress tolerance. Therefore, three strains, *Streptomyces* sp. Da 81-11, *Streptomyces* sp. Da 82-9, and *Streptomyces* sp. Da 82-17, which exhibited the highest solubilization and siderophore production, were selected for further screening.

The *Streptomyces* strains grew within a broad pH range (4–12) and exhibited cellulolytic, amylolytic, lipolytic, and oxidoreductase activities, essential for soil colonization, organic matter decomposition, and nutrient cycling. Moreover, upon inoculation on *Brassica oleracea*, all strains increased chlorophyll A by 8–14%, chlorophyll B by 20–27%, and carotenoids by 15–28%. Among them, *Streptomyces* sp. Da 82-17 showed the highest values, indicating strong PGP potential. Due to these results, this strain was selected for genetic characterization, and its genome was sequenced using Illumina method.

Using antiSMASH, we identified 21 biosynthetic gene clusters, among which those encoding the siderophore paenibactin were the most similar. Further analysis using RAST revealed genes involved in Nitrogen compound metabolism, including clusters responsible for denitrification reductase, ammonia assimilation, and nitrate/nitrite ammonification. Additionally, we identified a siderophore-aerobactin gene cluster, and genes *dhbF*, *entF*, and *fhuB* encode siderophores that enhance Iron availability. We identified a phosphate-regulated gene cluster likely involved in P uptake and solubilization, with additional contributions from genes *phoD*, *gppA*, and *phy*, which play significant roles in P mobilization. The genomic analysis further revealed key metabolic pathways involved in stress adaptation, including antioxidant system proteins forming both enzymatic and non-enzymatic defense mechanisms. Furthermore, genes *ars*, *czcD*, and *copA* encode proteins that contribute to heavy metal detoxification, enhancing stress tolerance and adaptability to diverse soil conditions. KEGG database analysis revealed genes encoding proteins associated with Mg and Ni chelation, β-indoleacetic acid (IAA) synthesis (*trp*, *aldH*), as well as genes involved in cytokinin biosynthesis (*miaA*, *ipt*), suggesting their role in plant hormone regulation. Moreover, genes *budB*, *budC*, and *butB* encoding volatile organic compounds (VOCs), including 2,3-butanediol and acetoin. These compounds are known to enhance plant growth by promoting root development, improving nutrient uptake, and modulating stress responses.

In summary, the genomic features of *Streptomyces sp. Da 82-17* suggest a strong potential for plant growth promotion through nutrient mobilization, hormone regulation, VOC production, and stress resistance, highlighting its promising role as a bioinoculant in sustainable agriculture.